

Antibody Characterization Report for Pleiotrophin

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

Author(s): Riham Ayoubi¹, Sara González Bolívar, Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme¹

¹ Tanenbaum Open Science Institute, Structural Genomics Consortium, Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca, peter.mcpherson@mcgill.ca

Target:

Recommended protein name: Pleiotrophin

Alternative protein names: Heparin-binding brain mitogen 1, Heparin-binding growth factor 8, Heparin-binding growth-associated molecule, Heparin-binding neurite outgrowth-promoting factor 1, Heparin-binding neurite outgrowth-promoting factor 1, Osteoblast-specific factor 1

Gene name: *PTN*

Uniprot: P21246

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. This report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for Pleiotrophin. We used an antibody characterization pipeline [2] based on knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of commercial antibodies for Pleiotrophin by immunoblot (Western blot) and immunoprecipitation. A U-87MG *PTN* KO from Abcam was used in this study. U-87MG was selected based on evidence of appropriate Pleiotrophin gene expression determined using DepMap [3].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the Pleiotrophin antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Proteintech	27117-1-AP	51712	AB_2880763	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.33	Wb
ABclonal	A14054	1155060301	AB_2760909	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.08	Wb
Abcam	ab133517**	GR155553-1	AB_2938813	recombinant-mono	EP3040(2)	rabbit	0.05	Wb
Abcam	ab79411**	GR3431290-1	AB_1603350	recombinant-mono	EPR3041	rabbit	0.11	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP45356	QC17981	AB_1147791	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-118876	XC3523772	AB_2903376	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-94984	XC3524055	AB_2806790	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, **=recombinant antibody.

Table 2: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	genotype
ATCC	HTB-14	CVCL_0022	U-87MG	WT
Abcam	-	-	U-87MG	<i>PTN</i> KO

Figure 1: Pleiotrophin antibody screening by immunoblot on culture media.

U-87MG WT and *PTN KO* were cultured in serum free media. Media was collected and concentrated. Then, 25 µg of protein from concentrated culture media were processed for immunoblot with the indicated Pleiotrophin antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: 27117-1-AP at 1/500, A14054 at 1/500, ab133517** at 1/500, ab79411** at 1/500, ARP45356 at 1/500, PA5-118876 at 1/500, PA5-94984 at 1/500. Pleiotrophin predicted band size: 19 kDa. **=recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: Pleiotrophin antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture media.

Immunoprecipitation was performed on 1 mg of concentrated culture media using 2.0 µg of the indicated Pleiotrophin antibodies pre-coupled to either protein G or protein A magnetic beads. Samples were washed and processed for immunoblot with the indicated Pleiotrophin antibodies. For immunoblot, PA5-94984 was used at 1/3000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=2% starting material; UB=2% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; **=recombinant antibody.

Figure 1: Pleiotrophin antibody screening by immunoblot on culture media

Figure 2: Pleiotrophin antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture media

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All Pleiotrophin antibodies are listed in Table 1. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 62-6520 and 65-6120).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201). Cells were starved in DMEM high glucose containing L-glutamate and penicillin/ streptomycin.

Collection of culture media

U-87MG WT and *PTN* KO cells were washed 3x with PBS and starved for ~18 hrs. Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at 500 x g to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at 4500 x g to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were concentrated by centrifuging at 4000 x g for 30min using Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024) and 1x of the protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429) was added.

Antibody screening by immunoblot using culture media

Immunoblots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [4]. Immunoblots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins were visualized on the membranes with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual immunoblots. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated for 2hrs at RT with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation using culture media

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our SOP for immunoprecipitation [5]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µl of Pierce IP Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D). Pierce IP Lysis Buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) was supplemented with 1x Protease Inhibitor Cocktail mix. Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by several washes to remove unbound antibodies.

Starved U-87MG WT culture media were concentrated as described above. 1ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of protein were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml IP Lysis Buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and immunoblot on midi precast 10% Bis-Tris gels.

References

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2. Laflamme, C., et al., *Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72*. Elife, 2019. **8** DOI: 10.7554/eLife.48363.
3. Ghandi, M., et al., *Next-generation characterization of the Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia*. Nature, 2019. **569**(7757): p. 503-508 DOI: 10.1038/s41586-019-1186-3.
4. Ayoubi, R., P.S. McPherson, and C. Laflamme, *Antibody Screening by Immunoblot*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717510>.
5. Ayoubi, R., et al., *Antibody screening by Immunoprecipitation*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717516>.